

Research Article

Cure of the Major Autistic Features of Autism: Further Patients

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Received: 📅 2024 Feb 09

Accepted: 📅 2024 Feb 29

Published: 📅 2024 Mar 07

Abstract

Background: A new therapeutic approach aiming primarily at improving and curing the two major diagnostic features has been recently described. Injectable cerebrolysin was used as the main therapeutic component in this new therapeutic approach. Marked improvement or disappearance of autistic features in these disorders has not been reported with any therapy before. The first book which described the cure of the autistic features was included in Book authority's lists best books of all time. The aim of this paper is to report the cure of further patients with autism.

Materials and Methods: We have been using a new therapeutic approach aiming at cure of the two major diagnostic features of autism as the standard approach for the treatment of autism disorders in our clinical practice. Courses of intramuscular cerebrolysin were given in individualized regimen depending on the age and severity of the illness, and with aim of improving social interactions including response to name, looking at faces, and eye contact. Most patients were also receiving neuroleptics to control hyperactivity and other abnormal behaviors. It was not possible to record the treatment and follow up of all patients. However, patients included a boy with regressive autism, and a girl with cerebral palsy and autism.

Results: It was possible to document the cure of the two major diagnostic autistic features in another five patients including one girl and four boys.

Conclusion: Cure of the major diagnostic autistic features have been reported previously in thirteen patients. This paper reports the achievement of autistic features cure in another five patients, thus making the total number of documented cure 18 cases.

Keywords: Autism, Cerebrolysin and Cures.

1. Introduction

Early during the year 2017, we established the first child psychiatry (neuropsychiatry) consultation clinic in Iraq. The clinic was established at the Children Teaching Hospital of Baghdad Medical City with aim of providing evidence-based consultations and evidence-based medical therapies, and also providing a child psychiatry training course. In our work in this pioneering clinic, we were keen in documenting the scientific practices and the patterns of disorders through scientific publishing. The three major neuropsychiatric disorders were autism disorders, mental retardation and cerebral palsy. Autism disorders are lifelong disorders, and for decades no medical treatment has been reported to be curative [1-17].

However, we have recently described a new therapeutic approach aiming primarily at improving and curing the two major diagnostic features of autism which are poor responsiveness to their name and poor eye contact. Injectable cere-

brolysin was used as the main therapeutic component in this new therapeutic approach [18].

Courses of intramuscular cerebrolysin were given in individualized regimen depending on the age and severity of the illness, and with aim of improving social interactions including response to name, looking at faces, and eye contact. Most patients also required neuroleptics to control hyperactivity and other abnormal behaviors risperidone including trifluoperazine and prochlorperazine. Some patients also received citicoline as an adjunctive therapy to improve speech development [18].

Marked improvement or disappearance of autistic features in these disorders has not been reported with any therapy before. However, almost all the patients treated with the new therapeutic approach experienced some improvement and lessening of the autistic features during the follow-up period. Treatment was also associated with initiation of speech

and improvement of repetitive behaviors. It was initially possible to document complete disappearance of the main autistic features in twelve patients [18].

Therefore, we have been using this new therapeutic approach as the standard approach for the treatment of autism disorders in our clinical practice. We have been trying to document our clinical practice through scientific publications as possible [19-22]. It was possible to document cure of the major autistic features in the thirteen patients. He had autosomal recessive autism with mental retardation, and his younger brother was one of the first 12 documents patients who cured from the major autistic features [23, 24].

The first book which described the cure of the autistic features [2] was included in Book authority's lists best books of all time [25]. Therefore, we have been consulted about the treatment of autism from many countries in the world including the United Kingdom, Canada, United Arab of Emirate, Tunisia, Palestine, India, and Pakistan, and many of the international cases have been reported [26-30].

The aim of this paper is to report the cure of further patients with autism.

2. Patients and Methods

We have been using a new therapeutic approach aiming at cure of the two major diagnostic features of autism as the standard approach for the treatment of autism disorders in our clinical practice. Courses of intramuscular cerebrolysin were given in individualized regimen depending on the age and severity of the illness, and with aim of improving social interactions including response to name, looking at faces, and eye contact. Most patients were also receiving neuroleptics to control hyperactivity and other abnormal behaviors. Some patients also received citicoline as an adjunctive therapy to improve speech development. It was not possible to record the treatment and follow up of all patients. However, patients included a boy with regressive autism (Figure-1), and a girl with cerebral palsy and autism.

Figure-1: A boy with regressive autism

3. Results

It was possible to document the cure of the two major diagnostic autistic features in another five patients including a two and half years old girl who received intramuscular cerebrolysin 2.5 ml every third day in the morning (Ten doses monthly) for five months. After cure of major autistic features at about the age of three years, she was saying less 20 words and she was having echolalia sometimes. Therefore, oral piracetam 400 mg once daily in the morning, and oral citicoline 200 mg daily in the morning were prescribed to improve speech development.

Cure of the two major diagnostic features of autism was also achieved in four boys including boy with severe atypical genetic autism associated with mental retardation and obesity. The parents were divorced because their son and daughter were both autistic. The boy was included in a previous publication [18]. but cure of the autistic features was not reported during that time. The patients received intramuscular cerebrolysin for about one year (Ten doses monthly) and he was also receiving neuroleptics to control hyperactivity and behavioral abnormalities.

We have consistently finding that patients with severe autistic disorder behave at the clinic as the treating physician is invisible and they do not look at him or respond to him in any way. Before treatment this boy was behaving like this. Before treatment he was not responding to name and had no eye contact (Figure-2A). However, after treatment he had acceptable eye contact and was responding to name. It was possible to convince him to take a pen to scribble, copy a line or a circle (Figure-2B).

Figure-2A: Before treatment he was not responding to name and had no eye contact

Figure-2B: After treatment, it was possible to convince boy to take a pen to scribble, copy a line or a circle

Obviously, at the age of about ten years, he still had significant mental retardation and was not saying any word and needed more therapies to improve his cognition and speech. Cure of the two major diagnostic features of autism was also achieved in another boy who was included in a previous publication [18], but cure of the autistic features was not reported during that time. After treatment, the boy had normal eye contact, responding to name and normal interaction with the doctor as he was shaking hands with the doctor, and accepted to take a pen to try to copy a line and a circle (Figure-3A). He also accepted to take a photo with the doctor (Figure-4B).

Figure-3A: After treatment, the boy had normal eye contact, responding to name and normal interaction with the doctor as he was shaking hands with the doctor, and accepted to take a pen to try to copy a line and a circle

Figure-4B: The boy was happy to take a photo with the doctor

A third boy started treatment at about the age of three years. He was not saying any word and had no eye contact and was not responding to name (Figure-4A). He received intramuscular cerebrolysin 3 ml every third day in the morning (Ten doses monthly) for four months. He also received oral risperidone 1mg daily at night to control hyperactivity. After four months of treatment (Figure-4C), the boy was responding to name and had normal eye contact. However, he did not understand when the doctor was asking him to take the pen to scribble, and that was attributed to cognitive impairment. Therefore, he needed more treatments.

Figure-4A: Before treatment, he was very irritable had no eye contact and was not responding to name

Figure-4C: After four months of treatment, the boy was responding to name and had normal eye contact. However, he did not understand when the doctor was asking him to take the pen to scribble

A fourth boy with autism was also cured. He was not saying any word and had no eye contact and was not responding to name. After treatment (Figure-5), the boy was responding to name and had normal eye contact.

Figure-5: After Treatment, the Boy was Responding to Name and Had Normal Eye Contact

4. Discussion

Autism disorders have become increasingly known as pervasive developmental disorders especially in the United Kingdom since the 1980s. They are very complicated and multifarious group of chronic disorders that are characteristically marked by early impairment in social interaction and communication. Poor speech development, and repetitive body movements or behavior patterns are important associated features of autism disorders.

The diagnosis of autism is clinical and is based on the presence of the characteristic diagnostic manifestations which result from impaired social interaction and communication which cause the two major diagnostic features of autism which are the lack of appropriate responsiveness to own name, and the lack of eye contact.

The variation in speech and cognitive development result in the subtypes of autism. The mildest type of autism was the first to be reported in the medical literature and is associated with acceptable speech and cognitive developments.

This type was first described by Grunya Efimovna Sukhareva (Figure-6A), a Soviet pediatric psychiatrist in 1925, and she called the disorder autistic psychopathy.

Figure-6A: Grunya Efimovna Sukhareva, a Soviet Pediatric Psychiatrist

In 1944, Hans Asperger (Figure-6B), an Austrian physician reported children having the mildest type of autism which was first described by Grunya Efimovna Sukhareva in 1925. However, in 1981, Lorna Wing (Figure-6C) called the mildest type of autism Asperger syndrome.

The type of autism that is generally considered the classic type is Kanner syndrome which was named after Leo Kanner (Figure-6D) in 1943. Despite this type is associated with a normal or high intelligence, it is associated with significant delay in speech development

Figure-6B: Hans Asperger, an Austrian physician

Figure-6C: Lorna Gladys Wing, an English psychiatrist

Figure-6D: Leo Kanner, an Austrian American Psychiatrist

Autism disorders that are associated with subnormal intelligence but without significant cognitive impairment are generally associated with delayed speech and are generally called typical autism rather than classical autism.

For decades, autism disorders have been considered life-long disorders without curative therapies. Recently a new therapeutic approach aiming primarily at improving and curing the two major diagnostic features of autism which are poor responsiveness to their name and poor eye contact was described. Injectable cerebrolysin was used as the main therapeutic component in this new therapeutic approach. Marked improvement or disappearance of autistic features in these disorders has not been reported with any therapy before. However, almost all the patients treated with the new therapeutic approach experienced some improvement and lessening of the autistic features during the follow-up period [1-10].

Cerebrolysin is a mixture of free amino acids (85%) and 15% biologically active low molecular weight amino acid sequences which include low molecular weight neuro-peptides (Brain-derived neurotrophic factor, glial cell line-derived neurotrophic factor, nerve growth factor, ciliary neurotrophic factor).

Cerebrolysin has been used safely with benefit in a variety of neuro-psychiatric disorders including idiopathic mental retardation, cerebral palsy, brain atrophy, myelomeningocele, pediatric juvenile spinal muscular atrophy, pediatric Charcot Marie Tooth disease, kernicterus, and agenesis of corpus callosum with colpocephaly [31-41].

5. Conclusion

Cure of the major diagnostic autistic features have been reported previously in thirteen patients. This paper reports the achievement of autistic features cure in another five patients, thus making the total number of documented cure 18 cases.

Acknowledgement

1-The author would to express his gratitude for the parents of the patients who accepted publishing their photos.

2-Some figures were previously published, and the author has their copyright.

References

- Al Mosawi, A. J. (2019). Pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children. *Journal of Psychiatry Research Reviews & Reports*. SRC/JPSRR-102. DOI: doi.org/10.47363/JPSRR/2019 (1), 102, 2-8.
- Al Mosawi, A. J. (2019). Pervasive developmental disorders in Iraqi children. *Journal of Psychiatry Research Reviews & Reports*. SRC/JPSRR-102. DOI: doi.org/10.47363/JPSRR/2019 (1), 102, 2-8.
- Al Mosawi, A. (2018). *Pediatric psychiatry: An accredited training course*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). *Case studies in pediatric psychiatry: An approach to deep learning*.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). Clinical uses of cerebrolysin in pediatric neuropsychiatry. *Science World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(1), 1-4.
- Al Mosawi, A. (2018). *Asperger syndrome and regressive autism*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). New therapies for Rett syndrome. *J Bio Innov*, 8(3), 301-307.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). Childhood dementia: Heller syndrome. (2019) Baghdad. Iraq Headquarter of Copernicus Scientists International Panel Publishing.
- Al Mosawi, A. J. (2019). Heller syndrome in two Iraqi children. *Clinical Research and Trials*, 5, 1-3.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The use of cerebrolysin and citicoline in autism and Asperger syndrome. *J Bio Innov*, 8(1), 99-108.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). A Unique experience with mental and developmental retardation: Innovative Medical therapies for idiopathic mental retardation. *EC Clinical and Medical Case Reports*, 3(5), 42-54.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). Clinical uses of cerebrolysin in pediatric neuropsychiatry. *Science World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(1), 1-4.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The etiology of mental retardation in Iraqi children. *autism*, 1, 4-7.
- Al Mosawi, A. (2018). *A novel therapeutic approach for idiopathic mental retardation*. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The pattern of mental retardation in Iraqi children. Saarbrücken LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The pattern of cerebral palsy in Iraqi children. *Med Life Clin*, 1(1), 1001.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The pattern of cerebral palsy in Iraqi children. *Med Life Clin*, 1(1), 1001.
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). Cure of autistic disorders: Mission impossible is possible in an illustrated pioneering experience. *Archives of Health Science*, 4(1), 1-26.
- Al Mosawi, A. J. (2021). A Typical Autism Associated with Elevated Gonadotrophin and Precious Puberty: A Very Rare Association or a New Clinical Syndrome? *development*, 33(2).
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). Catatonia: A Rare Manifestation of Autism. *Medp Psychiatry Behav Sci*, 1(1).
- Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2023). The association of autism with

- self-injurious behaviors: An educational article. *Journal of Innovations in Medical Research*, 2(1), 5-10.
22. Al-Mosawi, A. J. Autism with Severe Mental Retardation: a Therapeutic Challenge and Expert Opinion.
 23. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2021). Autosomal Recessive Autism: Cure of the Major Autistic Features. *Scholars International Journal of Anatomy and Physiology*, 4(8), 120-126.
 24. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). Atypical Genetic Autism: Cure of the Major Autistic Features and the Need for Cognitive Improvement and Rehabilitation. *Medp Psychiatry Behav Sci*, 1(1).
 25. Al-Mosawi AJ. Books of Aamir Jalal Al-Mosawi included in Book authority's list of Best Books of All Time on December 15, 2021.
 26. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). Cerebral Palsy and Autism Associated with Periventricular White Matter Hyperintensity on Brain Magnetic Resonance Imaging: A New Disorder and Its Treatment. *Medp Psychiatry Behav Sci*, 1(1).
 27. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). Cerebral Palsy and Autism Associated with Periventricular White Matter Hyperintensity on Brain Magnetic Resonance Imaging: A New Disorder and Its Treatment. *Medp Psychiatry Behav Sci*, 1(1).
 28. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). Treatment of a girl from Tunisia with typical autism: Evidence-based medicine and expert opinion. *Biomedical and Biotechnological Sciences*, 1(2), 1-5.
 29. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2022). A girl from Pakistan with atypical autism: Expert opinion and a therapeutic recommendation. *World Journal of Radiology and Imaging*, 1(1), 38-41.
 30. Al-Mosawi, A. (2023). A Case of Atypical Autism with Mental Retardation in an Adult from Canada: An Educational Article and Expert Opinion. *J Brain Neurol Dis*, 6(4), 1-5.
 31. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). Clinical uses of cerebrolysin in pediatric neuropsychiatry. *Science World Journal of Pharmaceutical Sciences*, 1(1), 1-4.
 32. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). New medical therapies for the treatment of myelomeningocele. *Surgical Medicine Open Access Journal*, 2(4), 1-4.
 33. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2018). A novel therapy for pediatric juvenile spinal muscular atrophy. Saarbrücken.
 34. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). The use of cerebrolysin in pediatric Wohlfart Kugelberg Welander syndrome. *MOJ Clinical & Medical Case Reports (e-ISSN: 2381-179X)*, 10(1), 20-23.
 35. Al Mosawi, A. (2018). A novel therapy for pediatric Charcot Marie Tooth disease. LAP LAMBERT Academic Publishing.
 36. Al Mosawi, A. J. *Journal of Neurological Research and Therapy*.
 37. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2021). The early treatment of a boy from Virginia with ataxic cerebral palsy. *J Pediatrics and Child Health Issues*, 2(4).
 38. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). The novel use of cerebrolysin and citicoline in the treatment of kernicterus. *Online Journal of Neurology and Brain Disorders*, 3(1), 208-212.
 39. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). New therapies for the treatment of ataxic cerebral palsy caused by kernicterus. *EC Clinical and Medical Case Reports*, 3(4), 26-31.
 40. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2019). Agenesis of corpus callosum with colpocephaly: A novel therapy. Saarbrücken LAP Lambert Academic Publishing.
 41. Al-Mosawi, A. J. (2020). The use of piracetam and cerebrolysin in the treatment of agenesis of corpus callosum with colpocephaly. *EC clinical and medical case reports*, 3(1), 01-05.